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Combined project-based learning and teacher-practical demonstrations to help acquire global engineering skills

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ABSTRACT

This article outlines the development of a Project-Based Learning (PBL) course for first-year students at SUPMECA, a French engineering school. In the French Grande Ecole system, engineering students are recruited after a two-year preparation, which is equivalent to the first two years of a degree course. The objective of this form of pedagogy is to engage the students throughout the module and to illustrate the theoretical contributions by solving a technological problem. The course covers mechanical dimensioning methods. The course includes a part of teacher-practical demonstration which decreases as the course goes by. This pedagogical scenario is based on the cognitive load theory and Bruner's constructivist theory. It has been developed by relying on the six points of the encouragement process defined by Bruner, with a concrete objective, to allow the students to go beyond the basic skills of dimensioning and to allow them to acquire the more global skills of engineering.

The implementation of project-based teaching combined with teacher-led instruction makes it possible to compensate for the lack of experience and autonomy of freshmen, while at the same time engaging them within the first few minutes of the module. Since this approach was adopted, an acceleration in the mastery of basic skills has been noticed and a longer period of time is dedicated to the acquisition of engineering skills, namely the convergence of each dimensioning in order to obtain a validated mechanism.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This article outlines the development of the Project Based Learning (PBL) at the level of a last year's Bachelor's Degree. The objective of this form of pedagogy is to strongly involve the students throughout the module and to justify the theoretical contributions by solving a technological problem. The module in question is the module of mechanical dimensioning method of Supméca a French engineering school. This school issues a Master's Degree.

While the teaching methods used in primary and secondary education are frequently renewed in France at the instigation of teachers and inspectors, higher education remains relatively traditional in its practices. Recently, some colleagues have felt the need to put the application back at the heart of their theoretical teaching. This need is induced by the difficulty of covering all the knowledge deductively before its application. The statement by B. Raucent [1] illustrates this purpose: « As a result of the increase in knowledge, it has becoming practically impossible for students to learn all that they need before being able to design a machine ».

It is therefore tempting to make the students “learn by doing”, even if it doesn't cover some parts of the theoretical knowledge. The other argument that supports this type of learning is the lack of motivation the students have for the magisterial courses. The role-play allowed scenarios favouring interaction between students and teacher [2]

2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The dimensioning module has existed for a few years and evolved to tend more and more towards a teaching by project.

However, teachers involved in this module tried to answer these few questions:

- How to more closely link the contributions of knowledge to the project;
- How make the students strongly invest efforts at the beginning of the module and avoid learning obstructions;
- How to allow students to understand the dimensioning as a whole in the given time for this module...

Project based learning and problem based learning are widely used in educational approaches [3, 4]. For our project we follow globally theoretical and applied principles of Project based learning [3]. But in point of view of our experience and taking into account the prior formation of our students (preparatory courses for engineering school contest), we estimate that

The pedagogical form known as "pedagogy by project" is difficult to apply in the first years of university studies because of the low level of autonomy and individual responsibility that the students have. The question of what the student actually learns from the initial program as well as the evaluation of the competences acquired by the students in this type of pedagogy also remains an open problem.

Thus we propose to combine two pedagogies. To the pedagogy by project format, we add a pedagogy by example based on a regressive part of intervention by the teacher along the project.

This pedagogical scenario is based on the cognitive load theory and Bruner's constructivist theory. It has been built by relying on the six points of the encouragement process defined by Bruner [5], with a concrete objective, to allow the students to go beyond the basic skills of dimensioning and allow them to acquire the more global skills of engineering.

So the author decided to promote learning by manipulating cognitive load because for students with little prior knowledge, solving problems seems to cause significant cognitive load that can interfere with learning [6]. To remedy this difficulty, one of the solutions is to propose to the learner, problems solved to analyse or to complete [7], [8]. The initial state of the problem, the goal to be achieved and a partial solution are given, the solution must be completed by the learner [9]. These problems to complete facilitate the transition between the study of the examples and the complete resolution of problems they are also a source of progress.

Bruner's constructivist theory, refers to a definition of the guardianship process: « It is the means by which a specialist helps a person less specialized than him ». The constructivist theory is linked to the concept of "proximal zone of development" defined by Lev Vygotski.

A part of the objectives of this theory is to make the learner able to:

- Solve a problem,
- Carry out a task,
- Reach a goal that would have been, without assistance, beyond its possibilities.

Teacher support is about taking over the elements of the task that initially exceed the beginner's abilities, and allowing them to focus on the elements that remain in their area of expertise and bring them to achievement.

J. Bruner details this six-point support process:

1 - **Enlistment**: engage learner interest and adherence

2 – **Reduced degrees of freedom**: the tutor fills the gaps and lets the learner develop the constituent sub-routines that he can achieve.

3 – **Maintain orientation**: the tutor must maintain the pursuit of the defined goal. (Deployment of enthusiasm and sympathy to maintain motivation)

4 - **Signalling of the determining characteristics**: the task of the tutor is to make aware of the differences between the achievement of the student and the success criteria.

5 – **Control of frustration and understanding**: try to maintain the interest and motivation of the student. However the risk is to create too much dependence on the tutor

6 - The demonstration or presentation of solution models: it is the presentation, of solution models to solve a problem, which requires more than just the execution, it requires the students' presence.

This pedagogical scenario has been built by relying on these six points of the encouragement process, and the authors tried to respond at each by a defined solution:

- 1 - The chosen format of the project allows students to makes sense of the given theories
- 2 - The structuring of the project, allows the dimensioning process to be tackled throughout several steps. This, makes it possible to realize part of the process before a total taking into account of the entire problem.
- 3 – A parameters table allows monitoring and convergence of dimensioning and so maintain orientation
- 4 - The follow-up of students in each session allows the signalling of the determining characteristics.
- 5 – The follow-up of students in each session allows the control of frustration and understanding
- 6 - Solving examples using the basic configuration before applying this on their configuration serves as the demonstration or presentation of solution models.

3 DIMENSIONING PROJECT

This dimensioning project has as support a vertical wind turbine and more particularly on the wind turbine multiplier, see *Fig. 1*. This project concern more than 140 students distributed in 48 groups. At each session, 4 teachers supervise 24 groups.

Fig. 1: Main components – Framework of the study

The project follows the following structure:

Definition of the current situation and of the problem to solve, the problem has as support the multiplier of a wind turbine (see Fig. 2 and 3) for a given configuration

Fig. 2: Wind turbine

Fig. 3: Multiplier

Definition of the desired situation, the objective for students is to dimension the two multiplication stages, bearings, the drive shafts and the mechanism casing to a given configuration of an alternator's range, see Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Components of the wind turbine multiplier

Planning of the student’s actions, a global vision of the future works is given to the students, as much on the dimensioning of each component as on interactions of each dimensioning on the system and on the necessity of a global convergence.

Fig. 4: Flow chart of the project

Actions, the students' work (10 sessions of 4 hours) is based on courses and project resource documents available on the Moodle platform and on "examples interventions" of the teachers showing how they would size the elements of the given configuration. These short interventions are disseminated throughout the project and represent 3/8 of the global time spent on the training. Based on all this information, the students must re-enact these actions taking into account the whole system and the interactions between each dimensioning. The monitoring and the convergence of the dimensioning are done through a parameter table. This table is completed at the end of each sequence on Moodle, which allows teachers to monitor progress, possible mistakes and to intervene at the next session with the student groups presenting difficulties.

Parallel to the dimensioning of the students have to modify the basic CAD model on CATIA V6 (Dassault Systèmes) with their determined parameters

Evaluation of the action: two intermediate project reviews, in session, make it possible to evaluate the progress and the autonomy of the group (in addition to the follow-up, session by session via Moodle). The differentiation of marks between students is based on certain tasks assigned to each student. A final presentation and the writing of a calculation note on the basis of examples provided by the teachers are integrated in the assessment of skills.

The question of what the student really learned from the initial program [10] as well as the assessment of the skills acquired by students in this type of pedagogy remains an open problem [11]. But, through the parameters table, it is possible to follow precisely the work of each group, at each session and to evaluate the encountered difficulties. It is easy, for example, to detect if the problem is about solving mathematical problem, a lack of understanding of mechanical model or a bad dimensioning choice.

4 CONCLUSION

The implementation of project-based teaching coupled with pedagogy by example makes it possible to compensate for the lack of experience and autonomy of first-year students, while at the same time involving them strongly in the first few minutes of the module. In this project, students have been confronted with the real dimensioning problems and are able to understand the links and influences between parameter variations and dimensioning, an objective that we did not reach in classical teaching. The fact of solving a detailed example allows the student to have a better abstraction of the task and allows students to have a better overview of the significance of the concepts taught by the teacher. The structuring, as a problem solving task, and the activities which happen during the convergence phase, allows for an overall comprehension of the dimensioning methods. It is this form of pedagogy which allows to accelerate the mastery of basic skills and so spend more time on the engineer skills namely the convergence of each dimensioning in order to obtain a validated mechanism.

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